

A novel high temperature eddy current damper with enhanced performance by means of impedance matching

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Abstract

When an electrically conductive material is exposed to time-varying magnetic fields, eddy currents are generated inside the conductor which oppose the change in the magnetic field. When eddy currents circulate through the conductor they are dissipated in form of heat due to the resistivity of the material. For low frequency vibrations, eddy current damping force is proportional to the vibration speed. Therefore, damping of vibrations at low frequencies or displacement amplitudes becomes increasingly difficult using this technology. Typical damping densities of eddy current dampers range between 0.1 for most devices and 2 MN·s·m⁻⁴ for best-in-class prototypes. Those values are relatively low compared with, for examples, hydraulic dampers that can reach up to 4 MN·s·m⁻⁴. This low density limits potential applications of the technology.

In addition, certain applications like vibration isolation of aircraft engines may require the damper to operate at high temperatures. However, most of current damping solutions are rarely effective at temperature higher than 100°C because they frequently use NdFe magnets.

In this paper, a passive eddy current damper with enhanced performance for use in high temperatures is presented. The Z-Damper takes advantage from impedance matching inside a magnetic linear gear to amplify the input vibration motion, maximizing the effectiveness of an integrated eddy current damper. SmCo magnets and high-temperature components are used in the Z-Damper, potentially enabling operation in a wide temperature range.

A theoretical model describing the dynamic behavior of the Z-Damper is presented and a set of experiments were conducted to evaluate its performance. A prototype of the Z-Damper has been designed, manufactured and experimentally demonstrated in a temperature range from 25°C to 200°C under low frequency (up to 60 Hz) harmonic excitations. A maximum equivalent viscous damping coefficient of 35 Ns/mm, measured at 200°C, has been achieved. A damping density of 8.4 MN·s·m⁻⁴ is calculated.

Keywords: Vibration, Vibration control, Damping, Magnetic Fields, Eddy Currents, High Temperature,.

Introduction

Vibration isolation is a very common requirement in transportation [1], structural and seismic engineering [2]–[4], manufacturing [5] or in high precision instruments and applications [6]. In most of those vibration isolation systems, high damping coefficients are required in a compact and lightweight device.

Contactless magneto-mechanical components such as levitation mechanisms [7], [8], bearings [9], [10], clutches and torque limiters [11], gearbox [12], eddy current [13], [14] or magnetorheological dampers [15]–[17] have demonstrated a large number of potential advantages against their mechanical equivalents: they do not present wear, they have an extended lifetime and they do not need lubrication so they can operate in very extreme environments from cryogenics [18] to high temperature applications [19].

Eddy current dampers are typically composed by a set of permanent magnets and an electrically conductive dissipater. The dissipater is sometimes substituted by a set of coils in the case of active and semi-active devices. When magnets vibrate, eddy current are generated in the dissipater and then evacuated in form of heat to the environment. A damping force, proportional to the vibration speed, is hence generated opposing to the magnet motion.

Despite the potential of eddy current dampers, their applications remains rather limited due to its low density of energy dissipation [20]. Some effort is still required specially for damping of low frequency vibrations[21] or micro-vibrations [22]. The effectiveness of a damper is frequently determined by its damping density which is the ratio between the damping coefficient and its volume. Fluid dampers present a damping density ranging from 2.4 to 4.2 MN·s·m⁻⁴[23]. Commercial magnetorheological fluid dampers typically achieve maximum damping densities from 0.1 to 1 MN·s·m⁻⁴ [24].

A development of a linear eddy current damper from Bae et al. [25] achieved a maximum damping density of 110 kNs·m⁻⁴. A later development from B. Ebrahimi et al [24] focused on the optimization of an eddy current damper for low frequency vibration isolation. A damping density of about 0.74 MN·s·m⁻⁴ can be estimated. A similar damper using coils instead of a copper dissipater was optimized and tested by S.Haji [26]. A damping density as high as 2.7 MN·s·m⁻⁴ is claimed. However, in those three prototypes, the use of NdFe magnets drastically limits their maximum operational temperature to about 100°C.

Another requirement for dampers in certain applications is an extended operational temperature range. Elastomeric dampers are typically limited in a temperature range from -50 to 120°C. Magnetorheological, hydraulic and gas dampers rarely operate at temperatures above 80°C. Wire-mesh mounts, which can operate up to 300 °C, offer a very poor damping performance. In general, no useful technological solution is available operating at high temperatures (>200°C).

In this paper, we present a novel eddy current damper which takes advantage from motion multiplication inside a liner magnetic gear. The damper is named Z-Damper because its operation principle is based in impedance (Z) matching inside the gear. By this means, the damping density of an integrated eddy current damper is significantly increased. A maximum damping density of 8.4 MN·s·m⁻⁴ has been measured at an operational temperature of 200°C.

Thanks to the use of SmCo magnets and self-lubricated PTFE bearings and spherical joints the Z-Damper is able to operate in a wide temperature range. An operational temperature range from -50°C to 250°C could be theoretically achieved. Moreover new developments of extreme temperature SmCo magnets [27], could potentially extend the operational temperature of the Z-Damper technology to a wider range from -200°C to 550°C with a similar performance. In this paper,

experimental demonstration of the technology from 25°C to 200°C is provided.

The work here presented is part of the FP7 Clean Sky Z-Damper project which aims to the development of a new damper technology for reduction of vibrations in future CROR engines [28].

Principle of Operation

The Z-Damper is mainly composed of a linear magnetic gear and a copper dissipater. The linear magnetic gear multiplies the input motion from the vibration. This effect is called mechanical impedance matching and it is widely discussed in [29]. Then, motion of the permanent magnets in the fast moving stage generate eddy currents that are dissipated in the copper outermost layer of the device. Figure 1 shows a diagram of the Z-Damper and its different elements.

Figure 1. Z-damper cross section

The linear magnetic gear in the Z-Damper is composed of three stages: an input stage directly connected to the vibration source, a stator connected to the “ground” of the system and an internal fast moving stage, which is free to move. The gearbox provides a displacement multiplication between the input and fast moving stage. The gear ratio (“n”) can be calculated just by the number of permanent magnets and soft magnetic teeth involved in the gear [30]:

$$n = \frac{n_{spline}}{n_{input} - n_{stator}} \quad (1)$$

Figure 2 shows a diagram of the Z-Damper principle of operation.

Figure 2. Principle of operation of a linear magnetic gear.

Theoretical Model

The gear ratio (n) is defined as the motion of the fast stage, divided by the motion of the input (or slow) stage. Forces in the input and fast moving stage can be also related to each other. For a quasi-static ideal conditions:

$$n = \frac{x_{fast}}{x_{input}} = -\frac{F_{input}}{F_{fast}} \quad (1)$$

where

x represents the displacement and F the force of the stage.

The mechanical impedance of each stage is then defined as:

$$Z = \frac{F}{\dot{x}} \quad (2)$$

where \dot{x} is the speed of the stage.

Finally, the impedance of both, fast and input stage, can be related one each other as:

$$\frac{Z_{input}}{Z_{fast}} = n^2 \quad (3)$$

A more detailed model is required when dynamic conditions inside the Z-Damper are considered. The fast moving stage has a defined mass and it is virtually connected through an equivalent magnetic stiffness to the other stages. Figure 3 depicts a diagram of the Z-Damper conceptual design:

Figure 3. Dynamic model considered for the Z-Damper

Three main elements are considered: an input stage or slow moving stage (1), which is rigidly connected to the vibrating mass; a fast moving stage (2) inside the Z-Damper and the stator of the device (3) which is rigidly connected to the ground. A “virtual intermediate stage” (4) is defined inside the gearbox to assist the theoretical description of the device and interpretation of the proposed model.

This “virtual intermediate stage” presents a perfect displacement multiplication (n) with respect to the input stage displacement (x). An inertial mass (m_a) is magnetically coupled to the “virtual intermediate stage” by an equivalent magnetic spring of stiffness (k_a). The magnetic equivalent stiffness will only be acting when a relative displacement from the virtual stage and the inertial mass is induced by internal forces or external forces such as friction or damping.

Damping

Damping in the Z-Damper is considered of the viscous type [14] and mainly generated by the motion of the fast moving stage and dissipated in the copper dissipater.

It has been calculated that the dissipated energy in order parts of the gearbox is at least two orders of

magnitude lower than the eddy current dissipation in the copper layer. Therefore, those secondary losses will be neglected in the proposed model.

Therefore, the damping force will be proportional to an equivalent viscous damping coefficient (c_a), exclusively related to the speed of the fast moving stage.

In order to assume that the damping force is proportional to the vibration speed of the fast stage, a careful calculation of the skin depth [24] impact in the eddy current distribution must be carried out. For relatively low frequency excitations, the skin depth can be calculated using eq.4:

$$\delta = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\pi f_c \mu \sigma}} \quad (4)$$

Where

σ is the material electric conductivity, f_c is the frequency of the eddy current, and μ is the magnetic permeability of the material. For electrolytic copper at 200°C, the conductivity is reduced about 55% with regard to that at room temperature ($\sigma_{200^\circ C} \approx 32 \cdot 10^6 S/m$) [31]. The frequency of the eddy currents will be coincident with that of the input vibration. Finally, the permeability of copper is almost equal to that of vacuum.

The skin depth, at 200°C and for an excitation frequency of 60 Hz is calculated in about 11 mm, significantly larger than the thickness of the copper dissipater of the Z-Damper prototype. Therefore the skin effect will be neglected in the present paper and the damping coefficient will be assumed to linearly depend on the fast stage speed. A more detailed evaluation of the impact of the skin depth effect can be carried out using FEA models.

Dynamic Equations

Based on previous assumptions, the time domain motion equation of the fast moving stage under harmonic excitations and considering no additional external forces is:

$$-m_a \ddot{x}_a - k_a (x_a - nx) - c_a \dot{x}_a = 0 \quad (5)$$

x_a is the displacement of the fast moving stage,
 x the input displacement,
 n the multiplication ratio of the gearbox,
 k_a is the stiffness of the fast moving stage,
 c_a is the damping coefficient of the fast stage,
 m_a is the mass of the fast stage,
and ω is the excitation frequency.

Hence, the displacement of the fast moving stage can be defined as:

$$x_a = nx \cdot \frac{1}{(1-\Omega^2)+j2\xi_a\Omega} \quad (6)$$

where

Ω is the frequency ratio between excitation and natural frequencies $\Omega = \frac{\omega}{\omega_n}$ (7),

ξ_a is the damping ratio, $\xi_a = \frac{c_a}{2\sqrt{k_a \cdot m_a}}$ (8)

A normalized displacement (ND) can also be defined as:

$$ND = \frac{x_a}{nx} = \frac{1}{(1-\Omega^2)+j2\xi_a\Omega} \quad (9)$$

The force acting on the fast moving stage is proportional to the deflection of the equivalent spring k_a . Note that there is not a physical connection between the moving elements of the gearbox (except for the bearings) and magnetic forces are exerted at a distance. The force on the fast moving stage can be calculated as:

$$F_{fast} = -k_a(x_a - nx) \quad (10)$$

Combining eq.9 and eq.10 it can be demonstrated that:

$$F_{fast} = -nk_a x \frac{\Omega_a^2 - j2\xi_a\Omega_a}{(1-\Omega_a^2)+j2\xi_a\Omega_a} \quad (11)$$

By hypothesis of the magnetic linear gearbox, the input reactive force exerted by the input is multiplied by the gearbox ratio (see eq. 1), then:

$$F_{input} = n^2 k_a X \cdot \frac{\Omega^2 - j2\xi_a\Omega}{(1-\Omega^2)+j2\xi_a\Omega} \quad (12)$$

And the modulus of the equivalent input damper force:

$$|F_{input}| = |n^2 k_a x| \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\Omega^4 + (2\xi_a\Omega)^2}{(1-\Omega^2)^2 + (2\xi_a\Omega)^2}} \quad (13)$$

The presence of any other internal or external force applied to the devices should be considered as well. A straight forward improvement on the model should include the friction force observed in the Z-Damper at low frequencies generated by friction in the sliding bearings. The maximum value of the damping force including the effect of the friction bearings can be calculated using eq. 14:

$$|F_Z| = |n^2 k_a x| \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\Omega^4 + (2\xi_a\Omega)^2}{(1-\Omega^2)^2 + (2\xi_a\Omega)^2}} + |F_c| \quad (14)$$

where

$|F_c|$ is the modulus of the friction force.

In order to maximize the damping performance of the Z-Damper at a desired frequency of about 12 Hz, the fast stage resonance of the gear has been made coincident. By doing so, and as demonstrated in Fig. 11, the damping force is maximized at that frequency while is reduced at higher frequencies. This behavior is beneficial for minimizing vibration transmissibility through the complete frequency bandwidth [32].

The fast stage resonance can be tuned by design of the gearbox parameters or by means of incorporating an internal spring to increase the overall fast stage stiffness (which is a combination of the magnetic stiffness plus additional spring stiffness). A semi-active or active adaptation of the resonant frequency is also possible [29].

Device description

Fast moving stage and stator are mainly composed of ring-shaped axially-magnetized permanent magnets made of SmCo 32H which present a high resistance to demagnetization at high temperatures. The typical residual induction of the magnets is 1.12T and their typical intrinsic coercivity 2150 kA/m (normal coercivity 835 kA/m) at room temperature. FeCo alloy flux concentrators are placed between magnets to maximize the magnetic flux density. In the fast moving stage, a total of 8 permanent magnets are concentrically assembled with facing opposing polarities. Their outer diameter (OD) is 91 mm,

their inner diameter (ID) 61 mm and their length (L) 28 mm.

A total of 64 magnets (OD=52, ID=32 and L=3.5 mm) are assembled concentrically and with facing opposing polarities to build the stator of the device.

The input stage is mainly composed by 74 FeCo alloy laminated rings (OD=89, ID=50, L=3 mm) Titanium grade 5 ring spacers are used to control the gap between the different laminated stacks. Most structural elements of the device (shafts, flanges, rods...) are made also in Titanium grade 5 alloy due to its very good mechanical strength and relative low density. Self-lubricated PTFE bearings are used in order to allow relative motion between the different stages in the device. One self-lubricated spherical joint at each end of the prototype is used to connect the damper to the actuator and to the testbench structure.

Finally, the outermost layer of the Z-Damper is composed of an electrolytic copper finned shell (OD=105, ID=95, L=400 mm). The motion of the fast moving magnets inside the gearbox generates eddy currents in the copper dissipater. By the Jule effect, part of the vibration energy is dissipated to the environment in the form of heat.

Temperature sensitivity

Performance of the Z-Damper is sensitivity to temperature mainly due to change in the physical properties of the permanent magnets and the copper dissipater with temperature.

Temperature affects both remanence (-0.035 %/K) and coercitivity (-0.25%/K) of the permanent magnets. That reduction in the magnetic properties of the magnets results in a consequent reduction of the force capacity of the damper at higher temperatures as shown in Fig. 7.

Additionally, copper conductivity is reduced at higher temperatures, limiting the damping capability of the dissipater. How this affects the Z-Damper performance is complex and it will be further discussed in later sections.

Magnets operational point

The formula for calculation of the permeance coefficient (B/H) of a ring permanent magnet is:

$$\frac{B}{H} = \frac{4L}{OD^2-ID^2} \sqrt{\frac{L(OD+ID)}{2} + \left(\frac{OD^2-ID^2}{4}\right)} \quad (15)$$

where

L is the length of the magnet,
 OD the outer diameter and
 ID the internal diameter.

Table. 1 summarized the permeance coefficient and the intrinsic operational working points (H_{di} , B_{di}) at 20 and 200°C for the stator and fast stage magnets according to the manufacturer demagnetization curves. External demagnetization field (H_a) has been obtained from FEM magnetostatic simulations with ANSYS Maxwell.

Table 1. Magnets operational point

Stage	T [°C]	B/H	H_a [kA/m]	H_{di} [kA/m]	B_{di} [T]
Fast	20	1.76	250	560	1.09
	200		200	510	1
Stator	20	0.27	230	910	1.05
	200		160	770	0.95

All magnets operate in the fully reversible zone so there is no risk of demagnetization at high temperatures.

Further characteristics of the Z-Damper prototype are summarized in Table. 2.

Table 2. Z-Damper characteristics and figures of performance.

Property	Value	Unit
Diameter	105	mm
Length	480	mm
Weight	19.6	kg
Maximum input displacement	±5	mm
Multiplication ratio (n)	7:1	
Maximum damping force (30°C)	6500	N
Resonant frequency	12.5	Hz
Temperature sensitivity	-1.8	N/°C

Operational temperature range	[-50,200]	°C
Non-operational temperature range	[-70, 270]	°C
Equivalent viscous damping coefficient (12 Hz, 200°C)	35	Ns/mm

Experimental set up

Testbench description

A dedicated testbench is designed, manufactured and set up to demonstrate the Z-Damper concept. The testbench is mainly composed of a bench structure (1), a climatic chamber to control the prototype temperature (2), a 15 kN hydraulic actuator with hydrodynamic seals for high frequency actuation from MOOG (3), a 13 kW heat resistor with a 3kW high temperature resistant fan (4) and flexible high temperature resistant flexible ducts. Fig. 4 shows a picture of the testbench.

Input position is measured by a LVDT sensor with 0.01 mm accuracy. Input force is measured by a HBM U10M traction-compression load cell with a measurement range up to 25 kN and 0.02 precision class. Position of the fast moving stage is measured by a Micro-Epsilon optoNCDT ILD-1420 laser triangulator with 4 μ m resolution. Finally, air speed is measured using a Kimo MP 120S anemometer equipped with a high temperature-resistant Pitot tube installed before the entrance to the climatic chamber. PT-100 temperature sensors in a 4-wire configuration are used to characterize the temperature of the flowing air and the prototype temperature. Finally, data acquisition system is composed of an NI9217, NI9203 and NI9263 acquisition cards from National Instruments installed in a NI 9188 rack.

Test procedure

Static tests were performed in order to analyze the maximum input force and the input and output stiffness. Influence of the environment temperature in the force capacity of the device is also evaluated. During static characterization

tests, the fast moving stage is rigidly connected to the stator of the machine, forcing the fast moving stage to be locked. Copper dissipater is removed in order to lock easier the fast moving stage. Since no motion is allowed between the fast stage and the stator, the influence of the copper dissipater is null on the static performance of the Z-Damper. Figure 4 shows the test set up of the static tests.

Figure 4 Static test set up

In addition, dynamic characterization tests were performed allowing the fast stage to freely move. Dynamic tests with and without copper dissipater were performed in order to analyze the influence of the dissipater into the prototype behavior. Input sinusoidal excitations from 0 to 60 Hz were then induced in the input stage at different temperatures from room temperature to 200°C.

In the dynamic tests performed at room temperature, the position of the fast moving stage is also measured with the laser triangulator. Figure 5 shows test set up at room temperature without copper dissipater:

Figure 5. Dynamic test set up without copper dissipater

Figure 6 shows the Z-Damper with the copper dissipater installed into the climatic chamber and ready to be tested.

Figure 6 Dynamic test set up with copper dissipater.

Experimental results

Static characterization tests

Figure 7 shows the input maximum force vs. temperature of the Z-Damper. The maximum force before slip (stall force), is reduced at higher temperatures. This is mainly due to the sensitivity of the magnetization of the permanent magnets to temperature.

Figure 7 Z-Damper maximum force vs. temperature

Dynamic characterization tests at RT

The behavior of the Z-damper has been characterized at room temperature. Both, input and fast moving stage displacements, are shown in Figure 8 in a typical dynamic sweep test with a harmonic input vibration of 1 mm input amplitude and frequencies between 0.1 and 50 Hz:

Figure 8 Input and fast moving stage position vs. time during dynamic characterization tests at room temperature

The speed of the fast moving stage is also highly amplified. Fig. 9, shows the input and fast stage speed vs. time for the same test in Fig. 8.

Figure 9 Input and fast moving stage speed vs. time during dynamic characterization tests at room temperature

The normalized displacement at room temperature of the Z-Damper with and without copper dissipater is depicted in Figure 10. A good correlation between the experimental results and the theoretical prediction of eq.9 is observed.

Figure 10 Normalized displacement vs. frequency at room temperature with and without copper dissipater.

Both results fit reasonably well the behavior of a linear harmonic oscillator. By the inclusion of the copper dissipater, damping is highly increased becoming the fast moving stage an overdamped oscillator ($\xi > 1$).

Dynamic characterization tests at high temperatures

The Z-Damper prototype has been tested in a bandwidth from 0 to 60 Hz at various operational temperatures (from RT to up to 200°C) for an input harmonic vibration of ± 2 mm amplitude.

Ventilation air is required to evacuate the heat generated during tests. Table 3 summarizes the air cross flow used for venting at different temperatures.

Table 3 Ventilation air flow at different temperatures

Temperature [°C]	Air flow [kg/s]	Air speed [m/s]
30	0.2	1
80	0.3	1.5
120	0.6	2.5
160	0.9	5
200	1.4	7

Figure 11 shows the Z-Damper input force vs. frequency of the excitation. Experimental results are in reasonable agreement with predictions of eq. 14. A very good fit at the resonance region is observed. At lower and higher frequencies, some divergence is clearly observed.

Figure 11 Z-Damper theoretical and experimental input force (25°C) vs. frequency

When operating at 200°C, the stiffness (k_a) is slightly reduced ($k_{a(200^\circ\text{C})}=50$ N/mm) due to the influence of the temperature on the magnetization of the permanent magnets. Figure 12 shows the input force vs. frequency for the Z-Damper at 200°C. Good correlation with eq.14 is also observed specially in the region close to the resonance.

Figure 12. Z-Damper (200°C) theoretical and experimental input force vs. frequency

Figure 13 shows the input force vs. input displacement loops of the Z-Damper at different temperatures at a frequency of 12 Hz.

Figure 13 Input force vs. input position of the Z-Damper when operating at different temperatures

Energy dissipated per cycle can be calculated as the area of the loop displacement-force. Figure 14 demonstrates that the dissipated energy per cycle is proportional to the environmental temperature:

Figure 14 Energy and power dissipated in the Z-Damper at different temperatures and 12 Hz.

This increase in the dissipated energy is motivated by the fact that the electric conductivity of the copper dissipater is reduced at higher temperatures, limiting the dissipater damping capacity. At a temperature of 200°C the conductivity is only 55% of the conductivity at room temperature. The reduction of the copper conductivity reduces also the damping ratio of the fast moving stage, allowing a larger displacement at the resonant frequency. From Figure 12, a damping ratio $\xi=0.32$ at 200°C is estimated.

This reduction of the damping ratio, maximizes the mechanical impedance matching effect, the input force and the dissipated energy as demonstrated by the results shown in Figure 14.

Finally, from the dissipated energy per cycle shown in Figure 13, an equivalent viscous damping coefficient, related to the input motion speed, can be calculated using eq. 15:

$$c_{eq} = \frac{\Delta W}{\pi \omega x^2} \quad (15)$$

where

ΔW is the dissipated energy per cycle,
 ω is the excitation angular frequency and,
 x is the input displacement amplitude.

This damping coefficient is maximized at the resonant frequency (12Hz) and is shown, for various environmental temperatures, in Figure 15.

Figure 15 Equivalent viscous damping coefficient at 12 Hz vs. Z-Damper temperature

Conclusions

A new damper technology based on impedance matching provided by a linear magnetic gearbox has been developed within the FP7 Clean Sky Z-Damper project. The damper consists in a magnetic gearbox with a multiplication gear ratio $n=7$ and with an internal resonance at 12Hz. Damping is generated by eddy current dissipation on an integrated copper dissipater. The Z-Damper has been designed to operate continuously in environments up to 200°C.

A theoretical model is proposed in this paper and compared to experimental results in good agreement.

Both, permanent magnet and copper electromagnetic properties are dependent with temperature. That dependency is analyzed in the paper and the influence of such sensitivity in the damper performance experimentally characterized.

The potential of the technology has been demonstrated in a large temperature range from room temperature to 200°C. An equivalent viscous damping coefficient of 35 Ns/mm at 200°C has been observed for the tuned frequency of 12 Hz. Then, a damping density about $8 \text{ MN} \cdot \text{s} \cdot \text{m}^{-4}$ can be estimated, at least three times larger than other eddy current dampers operating at room temperature with stronger magnetic materials.

This new technology opens new design opportunities for mechanical and structural engineers which require effective and compact damping devices for a wide range of applications, even in extreme temperature environments.

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